

or translated into higher yields. Early vigor was probably sacrificed to ensure a better canopy structure at the late growth stages and better partitioning of photosynthates to grain. This was well exhibited by the hybrids, especially MTUHR2033, MTUHR2020, and MTUHR2037, which had significantly higher grain yields. These hybrids also recorded greater BMP and HI. Though the check varieties and hybrids did not differ for BMP, the hybrids showed a superior performance because of more grains per panicle, which was indicated by a higher HI. Two hybrids, MTUHR2024 and MTUHR2029, however, showed an inferior performance compared with the best check Chaitanya in BMP, HI, and grain yield.

Heterosis is a highly cross-specific phenomenon. To use heterosis successfully to increase grain yield, parental genotypes need to be selected from modern cultivars with a high potential. The physiological efficiency of F_1 hybrids at the vegetative stage is a useful indication of heterosis for grain yield. MTUHR2033 and MTUHR2020, which showed such physiological efficiency, hold good promise. ■

Performance of hybrid rice in south Karnataka

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At the agricultural research stations at Honnaville and Kathalagere, we evaluated elite hybrids. We also investigated the fixing of isolation distance, number of seedlings to be planted hill⁻¹, and N management. Among the various hybrids tested in 1991-94, IR58025A / IR9761-19-1R was found to be superior to inbred variety Mangala. This hybrid recorded an average yield of 5.6 and 4.9 t ha⁻¹, respectively, at Honnaville and Kathalagere. Mangala yielded 3.8 and 3.6 t ha⁻¹, respectively, at those two centers. This hybrid also performed well in on-farm trials in the districts of Chikamagalore, Hassan, Mysore, and Shimoga, with a mean grain yield of 5.9 t ha⁻¹ vs 4.7 t ha⁻¹ for Mangala. This hybrid was named Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and released for general cultivation in the southern transition zone.

Similarly, another F_1 hybrid, IR58025A / KMR 3, had an average yield of 6.6 t ha⁻¹ vs 5.1 t ha⁻¹ for Jaya. This hybrid was found promising because it matured in 125-130 d, similar to the popular inbred variety. In 12 on-farm trials, this hybrid registered a mean grain yield of 7.3 t ha⁻¹ vs 6.0 t ha⁻¹ for the standard check Jaya. This hybrid was named Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 and released for general cultivation in 1996. The present recommended dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹ for the varieties was found to be equally effective for the two hybrids. There was no difference in yield among plots planted with one, two, three, four, or five seedlings hill⁻¹ in both the dry and wet seasons. Tillering ability in the hybrids was found to be very good. Therefore, planting 1 seedling hill⁻¹ ensured an economical seed input cost. In the studies conducted on isolation distance, seed set decreased with every increase in the isolation distance. This called for a revision of isolation distance for each hybrid through investigations at specific locations. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of salinity on growth, chlorophyll content, and flag leaf area of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) genotypes

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Rice is the most important food crop, feeding more than half of the world's population. To feed this ever-growing population, an increase in the cultivation of food crops is essential, which is possible by increasing cultivable lands.

Lands in Pakistan that are available for cultivation suffer from problems of

salinity / sodicity. So we urgently need to select or develop salt-tolerant rice varieties or methods to increase the yield per unit area.

Although yield is the result of interactions in the genetic makeup of genotypes, it has been suggested that by increasing photosynthetic efficiency, crop production could be increased (Ashraf et al 1995). Photosynthetic efficiency depends on leaf area, chlorophyll content, stomatal response, gas exchange, etc. We therefore used a physiological-genetic approach to test whether genotypes sensitive to or tolerant of salt differ in their photosynthetic efficiency.

For this purpose, a gravel culture experiment was conducted in a growth cabinet maintained at 30/25 + 2 °C day / night temperature and a photoperiod of 10 h, to study the effect of salinity created by mixed salt (Na_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 , MgCl_2 , and NaCl in the ratio of 6.33:3.58:1:2.28) and NaCl only on growth and photosynthetic activity of rice genotypes. Thirty-day-old seedlings of five rice genotypes—BH-5-89, BH-3-89, RST-1-86, RST-2-84, and Bas370×NR1—were acquired from the rice section of the Mutation Breeding Division of the NIAB, Faisalabad, Pakistan.